

Editorial

The Synodal Way

‘Synod’ is an ancient and venerable word in the Tradition of the Church,¹ and it comes from the Greek word σύνοδος. Its derivative συνοδεύω means “to travel together with.”² The word σύνοδος is a compound word from two Greek words σύν (“with”) + ὁδός (“way, path, journey”), signifying ‘together along the way’ or ‘travelling together.’³ However, σύνοδος has two meanings depending on its form in the masculine and feminine genders. i) When it appears in the masculine (ὁ σύνοδος), it literally means a travelling companion or a fellow-traveller. The feminine noun συνοδία is closely related to σύνοδος, and it literally means a “group of travellers.”⁴ Therefore, considering the various shades of meaning of the term σύνοδος, synodality can be described as journeying together as fellow-travellers with the same intention, purpose, and destination. Thus, synodality - a synodal Church - invites us, the people of God, to live our baptismal vocation in the Church based on integral Christian principles of communion, participation, and mission.

It is not enough to know and agree with the notion of synodality or to recognise the need for a synodal church. Jesus teaches us that we must do it! Don’t just talk about it. Just do it! Jesus demonstrates this by washing his disciples’ feet in Jn 13:4-11. The synodal way is to identify with the ‘fellow-travellers’ (Jn 13:4). Jesus takes more than just the dress of a slave. For he “emptied himself, taking the form of a slave...and... humbled himself” (Phil 2:6-8). He voluntarily gives up his personal glory and becomes a servant to his

¹ International Theological Commission (ITC), “Synodality in the Life and Mission of the Church”, Vatican City 2018, no. 3.

² J. Swanson, ‘συνοδεύω,’ ‘συνοδία’, *Dictionary of Biblical Languages with Semantic Domains: Greek New Testament*, Bellingham 1997, 5321- 5322;

³ J.P. Louw– E.A. Nida, *Greek-English Lexicon of the New Testament: Based on Semantic Domains*, I, New York 1989, 200-201.

⁴ J. Swanson, ‘συνοδία,’ 5322. In the context of finding Jesus in the Temple, the Gospel of Luke uses the word συνοδία to indicate the group of travellers: ‘supposing that he was in the group of travellers’ (Lk 2:44).

disciples. He even removed any clothing that would get in the way of serving others.

Jesus is not only dressed as a slave but also performs the duty of a slave (Jn 13:5). True synodality is demonstrated in the things we do for others and the responsibilities we assume. If Jesus, the sovereign Lord of the universe, washed his disciples' feet, what should his disciples do? Synodality is identifying oneself with others, especially in their struggles and difficulties in life. Synodality is to lose one's ego and merge in the Church's collective consciousness. Synodality is to conform oneself to the mind and heart of the Church and the mission of the Church especially hearing the cry of the marginalised and those who live in the peripheries.

The synodal way is the way of true servanthood (Jn 13:12-16). In Jn 13:12-16 he teaches his disciples that their service to one another must be modelled after his perfect servanthood. The synodal way is to walk in the ways of Jesus' servanthood, to serve one another in love (cf. Gal 5:13). He showed us that "the Son of Man came not to be served but to serve" (Matt 20:28), and he taught us that anyone who wants to be first, "must be a servant of all" (Mk 9:35). Synodality is an invitation to imitate true servanthood by remembering that the Lord is our Master. It shouldn't be below the servant's dignity to wash the disciples' feet if it wasn't below Jesus' dignity. If the "Sovereign Lord" became a servant and washed his disciples' feet, how much more should we render such service to one another by stripping ourselves of everything that hinders service? Synodality is a call to serve our Lord in our fellow brethren, and servanthood is the required attitude. Without proper servanthood, we will never be able to put into practice synodality in our journey together. Without changing our attitudes and values inherited from the clerical and hierarchical Church, we will never be able to realise synodality in the Church. So, synodality is a call to transcend all that blocks us and hinders us for a better journeying together.

The Synodal way is Jesus' way. Jesus did not merely wash his disciples' feet; by doing so, he also taught them, mentored them, and led them by example. Jesus' servanthood is the pattern, the model, for our practice of a synodal church. True synodality finds its roots in the self-knowledge and the love that sprouts from it. As Jesus had self-knowledge of who he was, where he had come from, and where he was going, our self-knowledge as co-pilgrims in the pilgrim church will facilitate a synodal way of life in the Church. As Jesus's exemplary servanthood stems from his sacrificial love, a love directed towards

“his own,” our sacrificial love for others will motivate us to lead a life for others in the synodal journey of the Church. Serving others in their highest interest is the way to true synodality. The synodal way will not be ashamed to present oneself as a servant in the Church’s functioning. The synodal way impels us to “walk as Jesus walked” (1 Jn 2:6), to do as Jesus did (Jn 13:12-16). The synodal way urges us to relate to others with Jesus’ servant heart. Jesus is the example of true synodality, so our efforts to journey together must be modelled after him.

In the first article of this issue of AUC, Fr. Thomas Manjaly urges us to be ‘synodal-pastoral leaders’ for realising a synodal church. In the second article, Fr. Thomas Karimundackal proposes that Pope Francis’ dream of a synodal church could be a means to overcome the scourge of clericalism prevailing in the Church. Fr. Linus Dabre, in his article, argues that Small Christian Communities can be instrumental in actualizing a synodal church, especially involving the peripheries. In his article, Fr. Walter D’souza proposes a mission-oriented synodal Church. Fr. Nishant, in his article, explores the possibility of taking inspiration from the early Christians to live faith in our contemporary times. We have included two feature- columns in this issue onwards: the first column will deal with some of the aspects of Canon Law, and Fr. Roque Alphonso, in this issue, explained the rights of the Christ’s Faithful. The second column is meant to recall the pastoral memories of the Papalites, and in this issue Fr. Saji Augustine, a missionary in the diocese of Muzaffarpur, recalls his 25 years of pastoral experience as a priest.

This issue of AUC is also a tribute to Prof. Dr. Kuruvilla Pandikattu who shouldered the responsibility of editing AUC for many years. He has taken this journal to its heights from 2014 onwards through his creative editing styles and ingenuities. His artistic mind always resulted in something beautiful in the journal and became a source of inspiration for others. His unique perspectives of the world, persons, things, events, culture, science, philosophy, theology, etc. found a reflective space in AUC. His capacity to create something original and his wide experience in the field of publication brought creative originality to the journal. So, dear Kuru, thank you for all you have done for the AUC Journal.

Thomas Karimundackal, SJ
Editor